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The Quest for Identity, Development, and Human Rights in Forlorn Manipur

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Abstract

The fierce clench of insurgency gripping Manipur has its genesis in a search for that elusive thing called “identity”. The identity movement that is now synonymous with insurgency in the state is pushing the people against the wall. The cry of the armed rebellions for social justice, springing forth from a deep-seated anguish of loss of its erstwhile sovereign status is perhaps dated now. This paper argues that “identity” is a dynamic concept and the ideology with which insurgency germinated in Manipur is passé. New ideologues of the state being left out of the development paradigm and casting it under the human rights umbrella are also typical. The result is a chaotic stalemate. What then, must be the answer?

Keywords: *Development, Insurgency, Identity, Human Rights, Manipur*

Manipuri Identity and Insurgency

Most identity movements are borne out of the urge to transform a society purportedly living in the dark shadows of a significant other and to promote the rights of certain groups of individuals who feel discriminated against (Langlois, 2001). Jenkins (1996) too says that identification of the self is tied up in most instances with emotional attachment. He further adds that where there are such emotional attachments, they have the capability of influencing actions. Insurgency in Manipur thus rose as a symbolic entity to proclaim such an identity against the significant other of the Indian Union. The following discussions will shed further light to this.

The Anglo-Manipuri war took place in 1891, whereby Manipur became one of the last native states of the British. In the subsequent interim, a momentous political event occurred; India’s independence from British rule in 1947. Manipur was subsequently merged with the Indian Union on October 15, 1949, and on January 21, 1972, it became a full-fledged territory of India and remained so for twelve long years. Meanwhile, resentment and mutinous feelings burgeoned as Manipur was ‘forcefully’ merged with an alien power Centre. The Manipuri intelligentsia contend that the merger was ‘forceful’ as a referendum never took place. There is also widespread ‘belief’ that Manipur had never been truly annexed by the British except for ‘some

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political autonomy'. This tumultuous merging with the Indian union marked the change from the familiar terrain and 'frame' of monarchy to a pseudo-democracy; being left to be governed by a distant Centre. Consequently, Manipuri identity is rattled by its history of loss of sovereignty, and a continual perception of hegemony. Today, the state and its people are grappling not only with 'identity' but also other intricate forces such as insurgency, development and human rights. This paper thus highlights the loss of identity and its consequent insurgency movement.

Lack of, or the denial of a sense of identification with the Indian Union is the fulcrum of Manipuri insurgency today. Conversely, harking of a lost sovereignty is no more palatable in the new social and economic order. This 'identity crisis' is further worsened by a bleak future resulting from a false consciousness of the alienated Manipuri society and its inability or refusal, to perceive the changed state of affairs over time and an impending state of anarchy. This argument is in the context of an insurgency-driven-identity movement with the ultimate political goal to erode the monolithic control of the state by the Indian union, and establish self-determination. Now, let us look at some key concepts.

What is Identity?

Taylor explains the concept of identity in three ways. Firstly, morality is at the basis of an individual's stance towards one's identity. Secondly, emerging contemporary trends have proved to be game-changers in establishing identities. Thirdly, the focus is on national identity as all individuals relate to a collective past. Democratic ideals, education and economic development have created new virtues in individuals and societies in the lived world. These are in turn drawing new vistas of both individual as well as collective identities that will be witnessed through various social movements in the effort of 'self-affirmation and recognition by a significant other' (Taylor, 1989). Identity movements arise out of the perception of being left out of the democratic loop, making a struggle for recognition its hallmark. The search for identity in Manipur thus fits very well in the conceptual framework that Taylor enlists. A deeply perceived sense of discrimination and felt wrongs by the dominant other dominate the discourse on Manipuri society and its present situation. Much of this pathos springs from its history as opposed to its diluted identity in the new socio-economic paradigm. Here, I look at identity in its collectiveness, where Manipuris nurse the ideal of being a truly 'Socialist' State, without disputing the significance of individualness. Identity is thus contextualised as a "collective

phenomenon” that “denotes fundamental and consequential *sameness* among members of a group or category...This sameness is expected to manifest itself in solidarity, in shared dispositions, or in consciousness or in collective action”(Brubaker & Cooper, 2000). I also present the concept of identity being unstable, multiple, fluctuating, and fragmented as we examine the situation in Manipur, driven towards separatist ideologies owing on many accounts to its ethnicity as well.

Polletti and Jasper also echo Taylor’s concept of morality as the basis for identity by stating that all of us get involved in some kind of moral protest to develop the kind of self we want. They also assert that “movements promote new identities as a way to gain power as well as to transform selves”. They further stress the prominent role of “collective identity in movements’ emergence, trajectories and outcomes” and also pose some questions of very high intrinsic worth. They ask:

Is the identity a group projects publicly the same one that its members experience? Are collective identities imposed on groups or invented by them? Do individuals choose collective identities to maximize their self-interest or do interest flow from identities? How is collective identity different from ideology? From interest? From solidarity? (Polletta & Jasper, 2001, p. 285).

These questions are going to assume more weight as we analyse the insurgency situation in Manipur, driven by a search for identity. Later parts of this paper will highlight how individual members of the group that comprise the collective identity appear uncertain about their self-interests. It becomes more complex, given that the ideology with which insurgency germinated is almost passé in the context of the new social, political, cultural and economic formations. The people of Manipur are now increasingly getting weary of insurgency and its unfinished and endless agenda of self-declaration. To elucidate, Polletta and Jasper define collective identity as:

...an individual’s cognitive, moral and emotional connection with a broader community, category, practice or institution. It is a perception of a shared status or relation which may be imagined rather than experienced directly, and it is distinct from personal identities, although it may form part of a personal identity (Polletta & Jasper, 2001).

Jenkins also adds:

...who we are, or who we are seen to be, can matter enormously. Nor is identification just a matter of the encounters and thresholds of individual lives. Although identification always involves individuals, something else, -- collectivity and history--, may also be at stake... identity involves

knowing who we are, knowing who others are, then knowing who we are, us knowing who they think we are, and so on: a multi-dimensional classification or mapping of the human world and our places in it, as individuals and as members of collectivities (Jenkins, 1996, p. 5).

It must be recognized that the process of identification over time is situational; influenced as it is by a wide array of self-identification mechanisms such as interests, frame of reference and culture. When a group of individuals share such commonalities, a collective identity is formed. This self-identification is in turn shaped by a self-understanding of the structural and political paradigms within which such self-identification occurs. The concept of self-understanding is therefore very much significant in the context of the irrelevance of sovereignty and the increasing relevance of democracy in the contemporary world. However, it must be noted that individual self-identifications put together do not necessarily make up a collective identification as situational contexts and frames of reference tend to change over time (Brubaker & Cooper, 2000).

How Identities Evolve

Identity is a multi-conceptual and dynamic entity, assuming various meanings and forms in varied contexts and scholars continue to theorise or contextualise it in equally varied ways. However, we limit our contextualisation to the notion of identity being dynamic and influenced by frames of reference, especially in the collective identity problem manifested as insurgency.

It is the relentless and reckless pursuit for identity that is spurring insurgency in the State. Such pursuit of a particular interest becomes entrenched in the individual or group identity as the case may be. Nevertheless, individual identification and collective identification may operate with wide chasms as interests vary or evolve (Jenkins, 1996). Identity is not an entity that people can possess. Rather, the interests that we possess determine our identity. This is frequently moulded to suit varied purposes and hence we must agree upon an ongoing process of 'identification' that determine action and chart the course of history instead of remaining hinged on the amorphous notion of identity (Brubaker, 2004).

It is highlighted that identity is not always a static; and if so, it is constrained by the context in which it is looked at. It is rather more profoundly enthused with dynamism in the context of changing paradigms of values and interests; driven by the new virtues of the modern world. Even as I

write this, an identification process is going on within me; where I identify myself with the several researchers and scholars, with immense insight into deconstructing identity.

The Identity Movement in Manipur

The identity movement in Manipur may have been distinctively spontaneous in its birth, insofar as it is driven by “local initiative and action by moral imperative rather than by bureaucratic planning” (Polletta, 1998). However, narratives too occupy a significant place in social movements as most narratives are emotionally charged; and they in turn establish the moral frame of the movement. We can develop self-understandings only over a period of time, for which we reflect largely upon our past; and where narratives have a great role to play. Nevertheless, it is also simultaneously important to reflect upon our present, and most certainly, upon our future; as narratives shape ideologies as well as actions and vice versa. Thus, we are all trying to continually establish who we are, caught as the world is in a dynamic motion of incessant social transformation. This is why rather than the ‘identity’ we carry or that which marks us; the enduring ‘identification process’ necessarily becomes a strong force as it is this process that can carry on any protest movement along. Insurgency as a movement thus needs to be examined in the light of all the dynamic forces of the new world.

Any kind of a protest movement germinates with the utopian ideal of positive social change. In Manipur, this was in the context of the altered framework of the state, subsequent to its merging with the Indian Union in 1949. This then sort of explains the well-entrenched relationship between identity and state processes (Clemens 1997; Stevens 1999; Meyer, et. al., 2002). However, the more pertinent and larger questions of, “*Why do they (movements) take the forms they do? When and how do protest movements bring about meaningful social change?*” need to be addressed. Therefore, in an attempt to understand the identity movement in Manipur, we will not lodge ourselves in any particular disciplinary approach. Meyer et al suggests that a ‘fuller understanding of social movements necessitates breaking out of disciplinary trenches’ (Meyer, Whittier, & Robnett, 2002).

Langlois also contend that:

Identity movements have three main and very distinct objectives. First, they denounce injustice toward minorities. Second, they convey the idea that specific cultures must be taken into consideration when public policies are elaborated so that they meet the specific needs of minorities.

Third, they demand greater control of their institutions—a demand that sometimes goes as far as self-government (Langlois, 2001). There is also a belief that individuals involved in identity movements promote their perceived interests based on their way of seeing things and their personal knowledge and values. Such values which shape interests of the members of a group or community act as a pivot in emerging identity movements (Langlois, 2001; Olson & Olson, 2009).

Understanding Insurgency

Insurgency is referred to as a protracted political and military activity directed towards completely or partially controlling a state through the use of irregular military forces and illegal political organisations. *Typically, insurgencies are responses to chronic governmental ineptitude and corruption, or to other forms of bad governance.* Insurgent movements use a variety of means to achieve their ultimate political goal of eroding government control and legitimacy. These actions can include guerrilla warfare, terrorism and political mobilization (Malaquias, 2001, p. 314; Snow, 1998, p. 228). Guerrilla warfare is understood as military conflicts using unconventional tactics to achieve their political objectives. This is preferred by insurgent groups opposed to conventional armies. Although such groups may not be well-trained conventionally, they have an edge of economies of warfare and know where and when to strike (Minix & Hawley, 1997). Malaquias (2001) further elaborates that unlike conventional wars, which is intended to control territory, guerrilla warfare seeks to destabilize the prevailing central political authority by de-linking it from the countryside and its population and, ultimately, de-legitimising it. These de-linking and de-legitimising processes often build on incipient dissatisfaction with prevailing socioeconomic conditions of decay caused by government incompetence, corruption, or both. Manipuri insurgency has a lethal fusion of guerrilla warfare, terrorism and political mobilization.

Insurgency is also interpreted as a syncretic phenomenon- one that joins diverse elements in a syncretic mix. It combines three elements: one, the “spirit” of traditional peasant “rebellion”; second, the ideology and organisation of modern “revolution”; and third the operational doctrines of guerrilla warfare. The first though now archaic remains of critical importance: it supplies the great passionate energy that moves insurgents. The second which originates in the American, French and Russian Revolutions, harnesses that energy and directs it toward great and not merely hopeful ends. The third more recent in origin provides the practices

appropriate to the energy and the visions. This mix has the force of a natural calamity (Desai & Eckstein, 1990, p. 442).

Certain pre-existing conditions favour insurgency. Poverty, rough terrain, distance from the centres of state power, large populations for recruitment, poor governance with weak local policing and poor counter-insurgency measures, rebels with superior knowledge of the local population, and foreign base camps that provide financial support and training (allegedly Bangladesh, Myanmar and Bhutan) are some of the conditions persisting in Manipur. Large scale prevalence of corruption and political apathy allow insurgency to persist as it becomes a device to justify poor development. A supportive local population thriving upon false consciousness where the irrelevance of the rebellion ideology is not aptly understood also continue to churn insurgency at their own peril.

Contextualising Insurgency in Manipur: Then and Now

Hijam Irabot Singh was the first leading revolutionary of Manipur. He was deeply provoked by earlier British atrocities wherein the Manipuri warrior, Thangal General, and the crown prince Bir Tikendrajit were hung to death in public after they were defeated in the Anglo-Manipuri war, 1891. Out of anguish and with the hope of paving the way for the identity movement, he founded the Communist Party of India in Manipur in 1948. Hijam Irabot held the ideal of an independent and socialist Manipur and wanted the state to be treated equally with the rest of India. The struggle was however short-lived as he died in 1951. Several other revolutionary factions were born after this, which are however beyond the scope of this paper. The ideology of all revolutionary groups remain to this day, “armed resistance to bring about self-determination”.

Hijam Irabot’s protest movement and other contemporary movements had the utopian ideal of positive social change. However identities or identification has evolved based on changing values and interests as stated earlier. This can also be attributed to a changed concept of self-understanding and self-identification. Individualism started overtaking collectivism. This further gave rise to diluted ideologies in the modern context, where goals and methods practiced by the rebels have changed.

Insurgents now apparently have close links with politicians, bureaucrats and businessmen and espouse the cause of a corruption-free State. However hushed reports have it that they are themselves steeped in corruption as extortion is the prominent mechanism to manage insurgent

activities. Meeting the requirements of arms and ammunitions, information network and a quality lifestyle especially amongst the top-rung cadres is an expensive affair. Few human rights organizations are even alleged to have links with insurgents (Mukherjee, 2007; Thomas, 2005) Deeper studies need to be conducted to establish how this nexus operates.

The positive side is that the people are becoming ever more impatient and weary of living in a trouble-torn Manipur. Up till the Nineties, fear loomed very large in every person's mind to even whisper about the undesirable face of insurgency that has pushed Manipuri society into an abyss of violence and under development. Now, the liberals, moderates, as well as the common people of Manipur are looking at this problem afresh as the dividends have gone berserk. Moreover, demands for secession and self-determination seem almost impractical in the new socio-economic order with fluid societies.

Identity, Insurgency, Development and Human Rights: A Heady Cocktail

Identity based insurgency in Manipur has reached endemic proportions and is quickly and surely thawing away the social fabric. The uniquely disturbing character of insurgencies presents serious challenges for Manipur and, more generally, the Indian nation state. First, their lack of clear political objectives as well as the extent and level of atrocities against both armed personnel and civilians alike make the prospects for peaceful conflict resolution highly problematic. Second, such conflicts can spiral into genocide because of the armed forces' constant and relentless face-off with the civilian populations. Thirdly, lacking an achievable ideological goal in the context of the new socio-economic order in which we live, several of the insurgent parties are sustained by more regional or even local factors of political economy, ethnicity, personal ambition and greed. This change in the rationale for insurgencies has been accompanied by a significant shift in both rebel strategies and tactics.

Nonetheless, the projection of the insurgents' armed struggle as a resistance to oppression of "Our land, our people" from the "foreign" yoke of the Indian Government still draws great admiration and participation, cutting across all ranks of the Manipuri population. A sense of false consciousness continues to envelope the people as there seem to be no way out of the pitiable state of affairs in Manipur.

Drawing upon this, there is an urgent need to pay heed to the Global Encyclopaedia of Political Science which states thus:

Revolutions that aim at a total transformation of society claim to act in the interests of the majority, but since the majority does not realize where its own best interests lie, it is left to a small avant-garde to make the decisions for it. In consequence, it is more than likely that a society will emerge in which severe repression seems to be permanently built in. Such a state may achieve striking results in various fields, such as the national economy or national defense, but to judge from past experience, it will not succeed in building a freer and more just society (Chattopadhyay & Sarkar, 2006).

There is also a flourishing drug trade and black money in a parallel economy that keeps insurgent movements thriving in the porous north east. This is evident from local dailies and other reports. Violence continues to rear its ugly head in every sphere of life. Manipur is almost invisible to public attention, and an ill-informed and apathetic Government continues to exaggerate ethnicity issues. It overlooks the situations that favour insurgency, mainly gross underdevelopment that keeps the region in a state of perpetual desperation. As per the 2011 census, the population of Manipur is 27,21,756, with a per capita income of Rs. 27,332 as against the national average of Rs. 46,117 recorded at current prices in 2009-10.

It may be counter argued that several welfare measures and developmental programmes have been introduced. But prolonged years of neglect and living in oblivion accentuated by rough and inaccessible terrain necessitate a host of unique measures. Promoting sportsmanship which is increasingly becoming a noteworthy asset of the state can be one such measure. Other measures include promotion of its rich culture, dance, drama and several performing arts, which are noted not only in India but all over the world. Handloom and handicrafts too occupy a place of pride in Manipur.

All this apart, unfortunately, Manipur grabs attention only when clashes occur between the Indian army and the insurgents. The armed forces, the paramilitary forces, and now even the state forces continue to lash out an indiscriminate attack on insurgents and civilians alike in their aggressive attempts to overcome the problem. Such acts are perceived in very poor taste as innumerable civilians continue to lose their lives or get maimed for life.

Role of the State toward Containing Insurgency

The state exchequer suffers a heavy burden in counter insurgency operations and due to frequent destruction of public property. Several lives are lost due to militant attacks, counter insurgency operations, and internal clashes. Bandhs and blockades create heavy losses due to disruption of economic activities. Insecurity prevents night-time economic activities and fails to draw tourists too. Education is one of the worst casualties of the state today. Low per capita income and continuing contestation between the state and the armed revolutionaries have thus created a pseudo-democratic situation in Manipur.

An unforeseen backlash could be a complete loss of peoples' support and identification with the ongoing identity movement, driven by incessant human rights violations and poor development indicators. Another extreme end could also be a complete apathy by the Indian Government owing to unyielding and recalcitrant identification of it as the oppressor; heralding an even more gloomy fate of clipped social and institutional networks. To avoid this pathos, the Government both at the state and centre must work towards securing the trust of the people and defending them; accompanied by a clear political vision that can counteract the insurgency vision.

Nonetheless, it merits attention that a new intelligentsia is emerging; spurred by the weariness with disorder and lawlessness. Many thinkers opine that the appeal of the movement is dwindling as it is nearing the end of its protest cycle in the wake of failed retribution. Local dailies and online forums are also increasingly getting replete with despair and disdain with the insurgency-torn state of affairs, the apathy of the political class, and a deep yearning for peace (Naorem, 2013; Phanjoubam, 2003; H. B. Singh, 2013; M. A. Singh, 2007).

Conclusion

Available evidence about how individuals sort out and combine different sources of identity, or about the psychological mechanisms behind collective identities are too little. People have a range of groups, roles, and positions available to them, and we know little about how they juggle and choose among them. Emotions too shape collective identity. Moreover, actions driven by identity rather than calculations of interest are especially likely when political, economic, or social change has destabilized prior identities (Polletta & Jasper, 2001).

Insurgency springs from the deep abyss of a feeling of deprivation, perpetuated by a significant other. It is the fountainhead of all things that preclude development in these heady days of globalisation. In Manipur, the harsh waters of insurgency has so inundated the land of all voices pristine that now only the call for secession rings loud. The State in the lap of insurgency, is certainly being rocked in the cradle of doom. The words of the Chinese Philosopher, Confucius, who said, "By gaining the people, the Kingdom is gained; By Losing the people, the Kingdom is lost", acquires great relevance in Manipur that is gripped by insurgency.

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